

Questionnaire of Best practices

We would like to benefit from your knowledge and experience by collecting information about best practices regarding instruments/projects to preserve biodiversity in the context of spatial planning. The information is for research purposes for the BioValue project.

[Read more about the BioValue project](#)

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* **Indica uma pergunta obrigatória**

1. Currently, how much do you think spatial planning contributes to halt the loss of biodiversity?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Not contributes at all

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

Contributes so much

2. Please name one or more good examples of instruments, policies and/or projects that show significant or potential improvements in halting biodiversity loss in the context of spatial planning. **Please refer the country of the example.**

3. What do you think is special about it?

4. Are you currently involved in any of these fields of activity?

Marcar tudo o que for aplicável.

- Architecture
- Landscape architecture
- Urbanism
- Planning
- Environment
- Policy Making
- Engineering
- Economics
- Social Sciences
- Education
- Management
- Agriculture
- Others

5. Are you involved in any of these type of organizations?

Marcar tudo o que for aplicável.

- Private company
- Consultancy company
- Non governmental organization
- Education, universities or research centers
- Others

6. In which country(ies) are you active?

7. How did you find this survey?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- In a conference
- Via membership list of a network
- BioValue website

8. If it was via membership list of a network, which organization sent the information?

9. Thank you for your contribution. If you agree that we may contact you for more details, please provide your e-mail address

10. First and last name

11. Please read [in here](#) our privacy policy and confirm if you agree. In there you can find our principles of anonymity, confidentiality, voluntary participation and the team leader contact information *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes, I agree

I don't agree

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